

Appendix: Methodological toolbox

Tool no. 3_1_1	
Title	MORPHmaster (Multilingual Online Restoration Project Hosting)
Category	Socio-cultural
Purpose of the method	MORPHmaster is proprietary software developed by Anatrack Ltd for ease of translating multilingual content by volunteers with minimal training
Effort in time	A 1-page tutorial (mostly an image of the translation screen). Ease of use is 4-5/5.
Number of objects investigated	Each of the current 5 multilingual sites has its own internet domain.
Data format	HTML, also proprietary code, in SQL databases.
Description	<p>A back-office for administrators handles users and translation (currently 54 languages) of objects which can be text, language-specific images or culture-specific links to as many single-language sites (in the System for Community Liaison) as required for language-regions that a user can select to reflect their geographic location. The system is constrained to non-commercial use by a license with not-for-profit third parties who manage the networks. The first instance, a stand-alone site, https://www.naturalliance.eu, is described in Chapter 20 of Kenward et al. 2013).</p>
Basic Literature	<p>Kenward, R.E., Papathanasiou, J., Arampatzis, E. & Manos, B.A. (eds) (2013). Transactional Environmental Support System Design: Global Solutions. IGI-Global, Hershey, Pennsylvania, USA. https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-2824-3</p>

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Linked material	<i>The most networks are:</i> https://www.sakernet.org (2015) https://www.perdixnet.org (2017) https://www.falconet.org (2018) https://www.naturalliance.org (2019) https://www.pro-coast.eu (2024) <i>this instance is the hub for the Community Sustainability Platform</i>